

Metal chelates of 1,7-diindolyl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione

K. Krishnankutty*, Joseph John and Babu Joseph

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Calicut-673 635, Kerala, India
E-mail : jjsh50@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 2 February 2007, revised 22 March 2007, accepted 22 March 2007

Abstract : A new curcuminoid analogue containing indole ring and its cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) chelates of ML_2 stoichiometry have been synthesized and characterized by IR, 1H NMR, ESR, TG and mass spectral data. Spectral data of complexes suggested the monobasic bidentate coordination of the ligand with the formation of a C_3O_2M ring system.

Keywords : Curcuminoids, metal chelates, indole.

In continuation of our studies¹ on synthetic analogues of curcuminoids (1,7-diaryl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-diones), the major physiologically active chemical species present in turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) and allied derivatives, in this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of a new curcuminoid analogue containing heteroaryl rings (indolyl) and its Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates.

Results and discussion

The general method of synthesis of curcuminoid analogues involves the condensation of an aromatic aldehyde with acetylacetone in presence of boric oxide and tri(*sec*-butyl) borate under specified conditions³. When the reaction was carried out using indole-3-carbaldehyde and acetylacetone, the major product was 1,7-diindolyl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione (Hdih), with small amount of the monocondensation product. Pure Hdih was separated by column chromatography.

Characterisation of 1,7-diindolyl-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione (Hdih) and its metal chelates :

The observed elemental analytical data (Table 1) agree well with the formulation of the compounds. Spectral data are in agreement with structure 1 of Hdih and structure 2 of the metal complexes. Thus the IR spectrum of Hdih in the region $1600-1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is characterized by the presence of an intense band at 1603 cm^{-1} assignable to the strong intramolecularly hydrogen bonded conjugated carbonyl stretching of structure 1. The broad band in the region $2800-3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest the existence of the compound predominantly in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enolic form^{1,4,5}. The bands at 1603 cm^{-1} of the

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of Hdih and its metal chelates

Compd.	m.p. (°C)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
			Found/(Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
Hdih			77.04	4.61	7.20	-
$C_{23}H_{18}N_2O_2$	165	-	(77.96)	(5.08)	(7.90)	
$[Co(dih)_2(H_2O)_2]$	156	3.61	69.50 (69.60)	5.12 (4.71)	6.52 (6.90)	7.86 (7.36)
$[Ni(dih)_2(H_2O)_2]$	141	2.72	69.84 (69.01)	5.03 (4.80)	6.45 (7.02)	7.30 (7.33)
$[Cu(dih)_2(H_2O)_2]$	>260	1.63	69.32 (68.57)	4.54 (4.72)	6.02 (6.95)	7.65 (7.88)
$[Zn(dih)_2(H_2O)_2]$	132	-	69.54 (69.92)	4.54 (4.45)	6.83 (7.02)	8.49 (8.010)

1

2

M = Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

free ligand, disappeared in the spectra of all the metal complexes and instead a new band appeared at $\sim 1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to metal bonded dicarbonyl function. The broad band in the $2800\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region almost disappeared in the spectra of complexes and revealed the presence of $\nu\text{C-H}$ of aromatic and aliphatic vibrations. A slightly broadened band appeared at $\sim 3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to the indolyl -NH groups. Further the appearance of a new medium intensity band at $\sim 420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu\text{M-O}$ also conform to the bonding of the metal ion as in structure 2.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of Hdih shows a one proton singlet at 14.5 ppm due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enol proton^{1,4}. The methine proton signal appeared at 5.7 ppm, the N-H protons at 10 ppm (singlet), aryl protons, in the region 6.9–7.9 ppm and the alkenyl protons at 8.25 (doublet). In the spectrum of the Zn^{II} complex, the signal at 14.5 ppm has disappeared which indicates that the metal ion replaced the enolic proton during complexation. Further the signal at 8.25 ppm remained almost unaffected suggest that the heterocyclic nitrogens are not involved in coordination.

The presence of an intense molecular ion peak at m/z 354 and other prominent peaks observed at m/z 245, 184, 170, 143, 130, 122, 117, 95 support structure 1 of Hdih. Mass spectrum of the Cu complex showed the molecular ion peak at 769 and 771 in agreement with the $[\text{Cu}(\text{dih})_2]$ stoichiometry. However the two prominent peaks at 805 and 807 in the 2 : 1 ratio indicate the presence of coordinated water molecules. Peak due to the removal of one or both the water molecules, the removal of indole groups in step by step, etc. are characteristic of the spectrum.

ESR spectrum : The ESR spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex at 77 K in DMF showed values of g_{\parallel} at 2.2750 and g_{\perp} at 2.0725 and A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} are 168.4 and $47.8 \times 10^{-4}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. These data suggest the presence of appreciable delocalization in the chelate ring¹.

Thermogravimetric analysis : The thermogram of the copper complex in air agree well with the $[\text{Cu}(\text{dih})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ stoichiometry. Thus removal of the two water molecules (found 4.41%, calcd. 4.27%) occurred in the $150\text{--}250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ range. The loss of the ligand occurred in two steps (DTG peak maximum at $353\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $485\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The percentage of metal oxide residue obtained also agree the formulation of the complex.

Experimental

Instruments used for elemental analysis and for recording spectral data are : Heraeus Elemental analyzer, Perkin-Elmer 2380 AAS, 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer (KBr discs). Varian 300 NMR spectrometer (CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO-}d_6$), Varian E 112 ESR spectrometer (X-band at 77 K), Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (using Argon as the FAB gas and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix), Mettler ToledoS R TG system (in air, heating rate $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$) and magnetic susceptibilities were measured on Sherwood Scientific, UK, at room temperature.

Synthesis of Hdih and its metal complexes : The compound, Hdih, was synthesised by the condensation of acetylacetone (0.5 mL, 0.005 mol) and indole-3-carbaldehyde (0.25 g, 0.0035 mol) in presence of boric oxide (1.45 g, 0.01 mol), tributylborate (4.6 mL, 0.02 mol) and *n*-butylamine (0.1 mL) as reported^{1,4} and recrystallised from ethanol-toluene (1 : 1) mixture to get spectroscopically pure sample. The metal complexes were prepared by adding slowly a solution of the metal acetate (0.001 mol, 20 mL) in 1 : 1 methanol-water to a refluxing solution of Hdih in ethanol (0.002 mol, 20 mL). Sodium acetate was added to maintain the pH around 6. After refluxing for $\sim 4\text{ h}$, the solution was concentrated to half the volume and then cooled in ice. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed thrice with 1 : 1 mixture of methanol and water and recrystallised from acetonitrile.

References

1. K. Krishnankutty and V. D. John, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 2003, **33**, 343; *Appl. Organometal Chem.*, 2006, 20977; K. Krishnankutty and P. Venugopalan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1998, **28**, 1313; K. Krishnankutty and Muhammed Basheer Ummathur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 639.
2. V. D. John, G. Kuttan and K. Krishnankutty, *J. Exp. Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2002, **21**, 219.
3. H. J. J. Pabon, *Recueil*, 1964, **83**, 379.
4. P. J. Roughley and D. A. Whiting, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1973, 2379.
5. N. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1997.